

RKUD 2325: Group Assignment

ISLAMIC ETHICS

The Ethical Implications of Surrogacy in Islam: A Critical Examination

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Introduction

Procreation is sacred in Islam, and the desire to pursue it is made intrinsic in the primordial nature (fitra) of a human being, as created by Allah (swt). The intrinsic need to continue one's lineage and establish a good generation is natural and actively encouraged in Islam through the permitted institution of marriage (Mehfooz et al., 2022). Marriage in Islam addresses the natural human need for companionship, family and procreation. Indeed, Allah has ennobled humanity, granting Man free will and placing him as the highest creation (Al-Qur'an 17:70). Therefore in Islam, marriage is a vital part of one's life and it is half of one's faith for it involves fulfilling a major obligation.

However, some women face challenges or experience the inability to conceive a child due to various physical or health reasons such as infertility. Medical advancements have enabled treatments and solutions through assisted reproduction, such as in vitro fertilisation (IVF), which has brought about revolution in reproduction and has become an important reproductive treatment that enables women with uterine defects and other medical issues to become mothers. However, IVF has also made surrogacy viable and created new prospects for many individuals to become parents, not just married couples, as an alternative attempt to conceive through medical means (Ansari & Saeed, 2023).

Surrogacy and its Types

The word "surrogate" originates from the Latin word "Surrogare", translating to "substitute" or "appointed to act in the place of" (Ansari & Saeed, 2023). Therefore, according to Raza et al. (2022), surrogacy refers to "the process of giving birth to a baby for another woman who is unable to have babies herself". It is a method of assisted reproduction, in the form of a third-party intervention, whereby a woman agrees to get pregnant and carry a

fetus throughout pregnancy, for the purpose of gestating and giving birth to a child for handing over to others to raise. The surrogate mother is then free from responsibilities to the child or its family. Surrogacy is a by-product of in-vitro fertilisation (IVF) techniques and artificial insemination (AI), and acts as a way to overcome infertility or inability to conceive. Resultantly, surrogacy has opened doors for unmarried couples, homosexual couples and single individuals to have a child. Similarly, married couples might also look at surrogacy as an option in cases whereby the wife is simply unwilling to get pregnant and carry a baby.

There are two main types of surrogacy, namely traditional and gestational. According to Ansari and Saeed (2023), traditional (or genetic) surrogacy involves the artificial insemination of the surrogate's ovum by the donor's sperm (e.g. the father of the child), and this process involves the surrogate's own egg. This method maintains the genetic tie between the surrogate mother to the child, shared with the intended father. Whereas in gestational surrogacy, it involves the transfer of an embryo created through IVF, whereby the fertilisation of the intended mother's ovum occurs in vitro and the resulting embryo is then implanted in the surrogate's uterus. It is deemed that there is no genetic link between the surrogate and the offspring in this arrangement. IVF underlines scientific breakthroughs in assisted reproductive procedures, thereby facilitating gestational surrogacy. However, there are significant disadvantages such as health hazards and psychological burdens on the surrogate mother through its process. This has prompted conversations on ethical considerations, particularly regarding the welfare of individuals involved in the complex procedure.

Legally, there are commercial and altruistic forms of surrogacy. The surrogate is paid for donating the egg, gestating the fetus or both in a commercial agreement, whereas in altruistic surrogacy, the resulting baby is gifted to the couple and the surrogate is unpaid

(Islam et al., 2013). The commercialisation of surrogacy has led to apprehensions and disputes over the commodification of women's bodies. Formulating legal frameworks become complex as issues are intricate due to societal norms and other aspects related to ethics, medicine, law, religion and culture, which has led to many individuals being against it. Therefore, different positions have been adopted by different countries on the matter. According to Ansari and Saeed (2023), "Only countries such as Canada, Greece, Israel, the Netherlands, South Africa, the UK, and some Australian states permit altruistic surrogacy. Conversely, countries with lenient legislation, such as Georgia, Russia, Ukraine, and several U.S. states (Arkansas, California, Illinois, and Maryland), allow for commercial surrogacy." It is observed that the ever changing environment underscores the importance of a detailed and deliberate regulation of surrogacy, especially when navigating the overlapping aspects of technology, ethics and sociocultural norms globally.

Ethical and Religious Implications of Surrogacy in Islam

Evidently, surrogacy has invited many legal and ethical debates in the Western perspective especially in its commercialisation as it gives rise to ethical concerns surrounding the monetisation of women's bodies. The exchange of money in the process of buying reproductive services has invited many criticisms, as the advanced assisted reproduction technology has challenged the conventional connection between marriage, sexual intercourse, genetic parenting and pregnancy.

In Islam, pregnancy is only deemed valid and legitimate through the intermingling of sperm and ovum of a legitimately wedded couple (Mehfooz et al., 2022). It is clear that surrogacy does not fall within the permissible and legitimate definition of pregnancy. The concerns based on Islamic ethics are apparent and it opposes surrogacy due to the problem of

lineage and other socio-ethical aspects of a human being, including in the relationship with the Creator. In formulating legal rulings, Muslim scholars take into account the Maqasid al-Sharī‘ah or purposes of the Law, which includes the protection of religion, life, progeny, intellect and wealth. This classifies the basic and essential necessities of human beings, within which the laws are guided by (Islam et al., 2013). Although Islam protects one’s lineage and encourages the treatment of infertility, there are limits by which Allah (swt) has set upon His creations based on His wisdom.

In verse 2 of surah al-Furqan, it says that “Allah is the One to Whom belongs the kingdom of the heavens and the earth, Who has never had any offspring, nor does He have a partner in governing the kingdom. He has created everything, ordaining it precisely.” Allah (swt) has made manifest several points that are foundational in Islamic ethics through this verse. Firstly, that He is the Creator of the universe, in which all of his creations have been perfected based on His might despite their flaws. Consequently, transgressing the bounds of Allah (swt) is a key issue in surrogacy whereby boundaries of relationships are challenged by involving a third party in reproduction. Secondly, Allah stated that He has created everything in a precise manner to maintain a social order in our lives.

Problem Statement and Methodology

While surrogacy offers hope for infertile couples, it raises profound concerns and is deemed unethical in Islam, particularly regarding lineage (*nasab*), motherhood and marital sanctity. Surrogacy also challenges the bounds set by Allah (swt) such as the fundamental Creator-Creation relationship in Tawhid, the equilibrium of family institution and the rights of the soul to know and maintain a relationship with the birth parents.

This study aims to go beyond a general critique of surrogacy by offering a deeper exploration of Islamic ethical reasoning. Grounded in the principles of Maqāṣid al-Sharī‘ah, it highlights how Islam emphasises the protection of lineage, the sanctity of the marital bond, and the clarity of parental identity—not only for Muslims but as a universal ethical framework. In addition, this research will examine the general ethical implications of surrogacy in non-Islamic contexts through case studies from countries like India and the United States. These secular models were used to illustrate the complexities and contradictions surrounding surrogacy practices, particularly in terms of exploitation, commodification, and identity ambiguity.

By contrasting these models with Islam's concise, clear, and holistic ethical guidance, the study ultimately aims to show that Islamic principles offer a more human-centered, morally coherent, and spiritually sound approach to ethical challenges like surrogacy. This research adopts a secondary qualitative approach through literature review, fatwa analysis and documented case studies to critically engage with both Islamic and secular ethical discourses.

Islamic Rationale Behind the Prohibition of Surrogacy

Surrogacy is unanimously deemed impermissible in Islam, and this ruling is grounded in clear ethical reasoning. A deeper analysis into key areas such as the pedigree and identity of the child, the sanctity of the marital bond, and the preservation of lineage, reveals the far-reaching implications of surrogacy.

A. Pedigree of the Child

Pertaining to the pedigree of the child, some scholars initially suggested that the child should be attributed to the surrogate mother, given that she carries and delivers the child.

However, Islamic sources clarify that lineage (*nasab*) is based not merely on birth but on biological origin, specifically, the sperm and egg. Surah Al-furqan (25:54) emphasises that human beings are created from water (sperm) underscoring the paternal role in lineage: “*And it is He who has created man from water and made for him [a place of] lineage and marriage.*” This verse supports the understanding that descent is traced through the biological connection, not gestation alone (Raza et al., 2022).

Given this understanding, Islamic law would assign rights such as inheritance, guardianship, and custody based on the child’s biological parents, not the surrogate. The surrogate has no claim to maternity, as the reason for the child’s existence is the fertilised egg of the intended mother and the sperm of the father (Raza et al., 2022). Initially, the Islamic Fiqh Council allowed surrogacy between co-wives, where one wife provides the egg and the other carries the pregnancy. However, after reviewing real cases, including one involving surrogate-born twins, the Council reversed its position. The key issue was the uncertainty over who the true mother is, the genetic mother or the one who gave birth. This ambiguity not only affects the clarity of lineage but can also lead to psychological distress for the child.

B. Sanctity of Marriage

Secondly, surrogacy poses significant ethical concerns regarding one’s sanctity of marriage, as it introduces a third party into the reproductive process. Some jurists have attempted to justify surrogacy by drawing an analogy with wet nursing, suggesting that just as it is permissible to benefit from the breast for nursing, the womb could be analogically used in the same way. However, a deeper analysis of Islamic texts reveals a critical distinction. The Quran explicitly permits wet nursing and even establishes legal familial bonds through it: “*And the [divorced] mothers may nurse their children for two whole*

years..” (Quran 2:233), and fostering relationships through milk are recognised as real kinship ties (Quran 4:23). The Prophet Muhammad (SAW) also affirmed that milk kinship carries the same legal prohibitions in marriage as blood relations (Sahih al-Bukhari 2645, 5111). Unlike surrogacy, wet nursing is clearly endorsed in Sharia and creates defined familial relationships (Mehfooz et al., 2022).

Surrogacy, on the other hand, lacks direct textual support and introduces ambiguity in lineage. There is a significant risk of mixing lineages due to the potential confusion of genetic sources, such as fertilisation involving donor sperm or eggs, or the surrogate’s own genetic material, which threatens the preservation of *nasab*, a core objective of Islamic ethics. In contrast to wet nursing, surrogacy is unable to establish clear genealogical ties until after birth and DNA testing, which undermines the Islamic legal structure of family and inheritance. Thus, analogizing surrogacy with wet nursing is invalid, and permitting surrogacy based on this comparison compromises the sanctity and exclusivity of the marital bond (Mehfooz et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the sanctity of marriage, as upheld in Islam, is also compromised by the impermissible practice of same-sex marriages, which surrogacy may indirectly support by offering a pathway to parenthood outside the traditional marital framework. This challenges traditional family structures, which is one reason why surrogacy remains illegal in Singapore. Despite the legal restrictions, some couples have turned to overseas arrangements to pursue surrogacy. A notable case occurred in 2018 (Annex A), when the Singapore High Court allowed a gay Singaporean doctor to adopt his biological son who was born through commercial surrogacy in the United States. Although surrogacy was not permitted in Singapore, the court granted the adoption on

the grounds that it was in the best interest of the child (*Hiring a Surrogate: 6 Legal Issues for Singaporean Couples - SingaporeLegalAdvice.com*, 2024).

C. Maqasid al-Shariah

Lastly, the ethical evaluation of surrogacy in Islam must be rooted in the framework of *Maqāṣid al-Sharī‘ah*, the five overarching objectives of Islamic law: the protection of religion, life, progeny, mind, and wealth. These objectives serve as guiding principles to determine whether a contemporary issue aligns with Islamic ethics. In the case of surrogacy, the principle of protecting *nasl* (lineage) is particularly relevant. The Qur’an explicitly condemns sexual relations outside of marriage, declaring such acts as transgression (Qur’an 23:5–7). While surrogacy does not involve physical intercourse, it still violates the sanctity of marital exclusivity by introducing another woman’s body into the process of procreation (Mehfooz et al., 2022).

Dr. Yūsuf Qarḍāwī emphasized that inseminating a woman with the sperm of a man who is not her husband violates *Sharī‘ah*, as it bypasses the lawful boundaries set by Allah. He cites Qur’ān 16:72: “*And Allah has made for you mates (and companions) of your own nature, and made for you out of them sons and daughters and grandchildren,*” underscoring that procreation must occur within the marital relationship (Mehfooz et al., 2022).

Surrogacy Outside the Islamic Framework: Insights from India and the United States

The ethics surrounding surrogacy vary greatly across different countries, often shaped by cultural norms, legal structures, and economic conditions. Two contrasting examples are India and the United States, which highlight distinct ethical concerns regarding transactional and altruistic surrogacy.

In India, the Surrogacy Bill of 2015 banned foreigners from engaging in commercial surrogacy. Under the current law, only altruistic surrogacy is permitted, and it is strictly regulated. The intending couple must both be Indian citizens and the surrogate mother must be a close relative who has never acted as a surrogate before. While this law was meant to reduce exploitation, it has raised new ethical challenges. An ex-surrogate in Mumbai who worked for a surrogate and egg donor broker criticised the altruistic model. She explained that infertile couples often feel ashamed to ask relatives for help, as infertility remains a stigmatised issue in many Indian communities. As a result, most prefer using anonymous third-party surrogates. The ex-surrogate also noted that foreign clients were once preferred by surrogates because they could afford to pay more, offering higher compensation than local Indian couples.

Critics of the current regulation argue that while commercial surrogacy has been banned, the legalisation of altruistic surrogacy may still open the door to coercion within families, especially among economically vulnerable women. The intimate nature of familiar relationships could pressure women into surrogacy without genuine consent. Furthermore, experts warn that the tightening of formal regulations has not eradicated commercial surrogacy but instead has driven it underground. The rise of an informal black market for surrogacy services in India is becoming a serious concern.

In contrast, the United States has adopted a far more liberal approach. Commercial surrogacy is legal in many states, including California. There is no federal regulation, so laws vary by state, but in jurisdictions where it is legal, surrogacy is treated as a legitimate business transaction (Hibino, 2022). However, this transactional model, while it allows for

autonomy and open market participation, can also commodify women's reproductive labor and create socio-economic disparities between intended parents and surrogates, especially when surrogates are from lower-income backgrounds.

These two case studies demonstrate how the ethical dimensions of surrogacy are deeply influenced by legal frameworks and social context. India's restrictive laws attempt to protect women from exploitation but may lead to unintended consequences like coercion and black-market practices. Meanwhile, the U.S's liberal and commercialised approach emphasises freedom and legality, but risks reducing childbirth to a contractual service. Each model presents its own ethical trade-offs that must be carefully evaluated.

Findings Drawn from the Case Studies

In light of the various surrogacy models observed around the world, it becomes evident that attempts to justify and regulate such practices, whether through altruistic or commercial frameworks, remain ethically ambiguous. While many of these approaches aim to protect the interests of the intending parents or surrogate mothers, they often overlook the fundamental rights and identity of the most vulnerable party involved: the child born through surrogacy. Islam, on the other hand, provides a clear and uncompromising stance. According to the framework of *Maqāṣid al-Sharī'ah*, any act that fails to protect *nasl* (lineage) is inherently unethical and impermissible. The preservation of lineage is not merely a legal technicality in Islam, it is a core moral and spiritual imperative that upholds family integrity, inheritance laws, and human dignity.

While humanistic legal systems may justify surrogacy on the basis of adult autonomy and consent, Islam shifts the ethical focus to the well-being and rights of the child, ensuring that no human being begins life with ambiguity in identity or heritage. Islamic law offers a

holistic, just, and spiritually anchored framework that protects all parties involved, most especially the voiceless child. Islam’s clarity on the matter, rooted in divine wisdom, reflects its perfection in safeguarding human dignity across generations.

Marriage and Lineage in the Quran and Hadith

Although the Qur’an does not address surrogacy explicitly, it provides foundational values that undergird the ethical judgment of such technologies. Chief among these is the protection of *nasab* (lineage), which is a higher objective (*maqasid*) of Shariah. The Qur’an states unequivocally, “Their mothers are none but those who gave birth to them” (Qur’an 58:2). This verse directly assigns maternal identity to the one who gives birth, not merely the one who provides genetic material. Therefore, surrogacy—especially involving third-party gestation—produces theological and legal ambiguity regarding motherhood.

The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) reinforces this concern with the hadith, “The child is attributed to the [marital] bed, and for the adulterer is the stone (i.e., nothing)” (Sahih al-Bukhari, 6749). Though this hadith addresses paternity in cases of extramarital intercourse, it has been analogically extended to cases of reproductive ambiguity. Surrogacy disrupts the sanctity of *nikah* (marriage), introducing external genetic or gestational contributors and compromising the clarity of familial roles established in Islamic law. In the realm of procreation, Islam views children not as products of human entitlement but as gifts from Allah. The Qur’an reminds us, “To Allah belongs the dominion of the heavens and the earth. He creates what He wills. He gives to whom He wills [female] children, and He gives to whom He wills [male] children... and He renders whom He wills barren” (Qur’an 42:49–50).

The desire for progeny is natural and even encouraged in Islam, yet it must be pursued within divinely sanctioned boundaries. Surrogacy—particularly when it involves third-party donors—may reflect an overreach of human will into the realm of divine prerogative. Accepting infertility, as shown in the story of Prophet Zakariyya who prayed earnestly yet patiently for a child (Qur’an 19:4–6), is not passive resignation but active submission rooted in *Tawhid*. From a *Tawhidic* perspective, engaging in surrogacy through ethically ambiguous means may signify a lapse in reliance upon divine wisdom. Thus, while Islam promotes medical treatment (*tadawi*), it must be tethered to the belief that healing and life originate solely from God.

The Qur’anic principle of *Wasatiyyah* “And thus We have made you a just (balanced) nation” (Qur’an, 2:143) enjoins Muslims to walk the path of moderation, balancing between lawful enjoyment and moral responsibility. In the context of surrogacy, this principle warns against both extreme permissiveness—which may justify any form of technological intervention—and rigid prohibition that fails to consider human suffering. However, even this opinion is a minority view and is met with caution, given potential social ramifications and the risk of commodification of motherhood. *Wasatiyyah* thus obliges the ummah to weigh medical benefits against broader social and theological consequences. It fosters ethical creativity without violating core principles, affirming that suffering—such as infertility—can be spiritually transformative rather than something to eliminate at all costs.

Islamic ethics places profound emphasis on family integrity. The family is not merely a social unit but a divine institution meant to preserve faith and values across generations. Surrogacy, particularly when it severs the unity between sexual intimacy and procreation, may reduce childbearing to a commercial transaction and challenge the sacred nature of

motherhood. Moreover, the commodification of the female body—as evident in commercial surrogacy—raises additional concerns. Islamic jurisprudence holds that the human body is a trust (*amanah*) from Allah and not a subject of ownership or trade. Hence, renting a womb is analogous to renting a sacred trust, violating both dignity and divine law (Kamali, 2010).

Understanding Rahmah as an Ethical Principle

In Islamic ethics, rahmah, which can be interpreted as "mercy," is a core moral concept that influences behaviour, laws, and social interactions. It is not just a feeling or virtue. According to the Qur'an, marital relationships are built on tranquility (*sakinah*), love (*mawaddah*), and mercy (*rahmah*): “And among His signs is that He created for you from yourselves mates that you may find tranquillity in them; and He placed between you affection and mercy” (Qur’an 30:21). This verse indicates that marriage is not only a legal bond but also a spiritual and emotional connection based on compassion for one another.

As an ethical principle, Rahmah encourages justice, fairness, and empathy for the weak and disadvantaged. This moral imperative, which calls on believers to maintain goodwill (*ihsan*) in their conduct, is neither passive nor abstract. The words *rahim*, which means womb, and *rahmah* are closely related, as Rosidin and Ja‘far (2018) point out. This linguistic link strengthens a moral aspect that mercy should be preserving, protecting, and focused on well-being, just as the womb nurtures and protects life. The womb is the main focus of surrogacy, which provides additional ethical significance to this relationship.

Absence of Rahmah in Surrogacy

The dignity and welfare of the intended parents, the child, and the surrogate mother need to all be carefully considered when applying rahmah to the surrogacy procedure. Based

on this prophetic ethic, Muslims need to conduct themselves in a way that avoids harm, exploitation, and injustice, especially towards those who are weaker. In this context, the spirit of rahmah is in contradiction with any activity that commodifies a woman's body, breaks her innate relationship with the child, or puts her in harsh circumstances.

The emotional, psychological, and relational costs of surrogacy cannot be neglected even in situations where the surrogate mother receives no payment for her services. Although they appear to be free from commercial exploitation, altruistic arrangements can contain familial pressure or unspoken social duties. Long-lasting psychological effects are possible for surrogate moms, especially after they develop a close bond with the kid. Islam acknowledges the strong fitrah (innate nature) of people, especially the innate connection between a woman and her unborn child. Even when done in an act of altruism, surrogacy may disrupt this fitrah and cause internal distress that goes against the moral principles of mercy and nurturing.

This concern aligns with the Quran verse that emphasises on rahmah and justice as essential values that guide human relations and family life, “Indeed, Allah commands justice and good conduct and giving to relatives and forbids immorality and bad conduct and oppression.” (Qur’an 16:90). When donor eggs or gestational carriers are used, a surrogate-born child may be deprived of knowing their biological or legal parentage. The clarity of lineage, which Islam values highly for social stability, inheritance rights, and individual identity, is compromised by this uncertainty.

On top of that, surrogacy raises major ethical concerns due to its potential to exploit women in economically vulnerable situations. Financial desperation rather than true

independence may influence consent, leaving the practice vulnerable to abuse. The Islamic concept of upholding human dignity is violated when the surrogate's body is used as a location for commercialised reproductive labour, typically without continued support or recognition. The mental and physical toll on the surrogate is sometimes underestimated, even in altruistic agreements. Concerns about exploitation of surrogate mothers especially in commercial arrangements have been widely discussed in ethical literature. As Wertheimer (1997) notes, payments in surrogacy contracts raise the risk of exploitation, particularly of poor women, highlighting the ethical need to protect their dignity and autonomy.

The deliberate isolation from the original mother raises ethical concerns, even while research conducted in non-Muslim settings has not consistently shown detrimental psychological effects, especially when children are told about their origins at a young age. Kinship ties and emotional bonding are highly valued in Islamic principles. The Prophet Muhammad s.a.w underlined the value of integrity, close family relationships, and consideration for the weak. Even if legal procedures are followed, purposefully creating an environment that could cause confusion or emotional distance from one's biological roots goes against these ideals.

Alternatives to Surrogacy as an Ethical Response in Islam

The Islamic ethical system is not reactionary; it is revelatory, proactive, and teleologically driven. Reproductive ethics—rooted in the sacredness of lineage, marital union, and divine will—do not permit unchecked medical interventions, especially when they destabilise metaphysical and social order. Islamic ethics encourage what is most moral, just, and caring rather than just tolerating what is legal (halal). A more consistent application of rahmah would prioritise moral alternatives to infertility, such as adoption, emotional support

systems, and medical procedures that do not entail third-party reproduction, rather than attempting to control surrogacy within the framework of Islamic ethics. These substitutes preserve the principles of duty, kinship, and caring without sacrificing lineage or dignity.

A. Permissible Reproductive Technology and Treatments

Islamic ethics oppose the use of a third-party surrogate, however reproductive technologies like IVF is permissible where both gametes originate from the married couple and the wife bears the child herself. Apart from IVF, Islamic bioethics supports other intra-marital interventions such as the artificial insemination within marriage and cryopreservation of gametes prior to medical treatments, such as chemotherapy. These procedures are deemed *mubāh* (permissible) so long as no third party compromises the conjugal sanctity of the marital bed (Kamali, 2010). It is recommended to train sharī'ah-compliant ethicists to assist couples in navigating halal fertility options, ensuring transparency, consent, and preservation of lineage.

Islam teaches that infertility is a divine decree, not a punishment. The Qur'an reminds believers, "To Allah belongs the dominion of the heavens and the earth. He creates what He wills. He gives to whom He wills [children], and He makes barren whom He wills" (Qur'an, 42:49–50). In Singapore, MOH (2025) has developed Marriage and Parenthood Schemes to support married couples with costs of conception, maternity and newborn care, covering Assisted Reproduction Technology (ART) procedures such as IVF. Therefore, married couples should strive to persevere through the permissible means of conception with patience and tawakkul in Allah (swt), and to avoid surrogacy entirely.

Essentially, a rahmah-centered approach to infertility encourages Muslims to consider the ethics of caregiving as well as the broader good (maslahah). It calls for a reexamination of reproductive issues from a spiritual and moral perspective, wherein faith in God's wisdom, mutual compassion, and respect for all individuals are valued more highly than merely biological fixes.

B. Adoption and Fostering

Adoption and fostering in Islam is permissible under a system of custodianship, without conferring lineage or inheritance rights falsely. The Qur'an explicitly forbids concealment of biological identity, "Call them by [the names of] their fathers. That is more just in the sight of Allah" (Qur'an, 33:5, Sahih International). However, the Prophet strongly encouraged caring for orphans and abandoned children, "I and the one who looks after an orphan will be like this in Paradise," and he held his two fingers together (Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī, 5304). According to MUIS (n.d.), it has long been encouraged by Islam as a tradition to contribute to the betterment of society. The Prophet himself, who is the best example in humanity, was fostered by his paternal Uncle Abu Talib, and the Prophet had also adopted children within his household, such as Zaid ibn Haritha.

Muslim families can ethically adopt children while preserving transparency in nasab, avoiding false claims of maternity or paternity. In Singapore, MSF (2025) has established support through resources for emotional counseling, public education campaigns and ethical frameworks for adoptive guardianship that comply with both Sharī'ah and modern child protection laws, supported by MUIS. Tan (2025) highlighted that the number of children placed in foster facilities had increased from 309 in 2013 to 540 in 2023. Therefore, it is highly encouraged for married couples to consider adoption or fostering when faced with

child-bearing challenges, as an alternative and to uplift the wellbeing of the child at the same time. Muslims should especially rise to undertake the responsibility and be exemplary to the society.

C. Islamic Counseling

Infertility in Islam can be a means of spiritual elevation, rather than social deficiency. Prophets like Ibrāhīm and Zakariyyā (peace be upon them) faced years of childlessness. Their *du‘ā*, patience, and trust in divine wisdom model spiritual resilience. Islamic counseling models should incorporate cognitive therapy, *tawakkul* (reliance on God), and *ṣabr* (patience), not to silence grief but to transmute it into existential purpose and communal contribution (Rizvi, 2022).

Conclusion

To conclude, while empathetic to the emotional trials of infertility, Islam calls for spiritual resilience and ethical restraint. Surrogacy involving third parties is impermissible and unethical in Islam. Ultimately, in an era of unprecedented biotechnological power, Islamic ethics reminds us that not everything we can do is something we should do.

The ethical complexity of Assisted Reproduction Technology (ART) within the Islamic worldview reveals not only a clash between human longing and divine order, but also a critical need for the reinvigoration of *ijtihād*—independent juristic reasoning—as a living, responsive instrument of Islamic bioethics. *Ijtihād* must rise to the task—not as a liberal license to permit all that is technically possible, but as a principled mechanism to discern how Islamic values can guide the ethical application of scientific discovery.

However, in the specific case of surrogacy, it is clear that surrogacy has transgressed the boundaries of Islam by violating the rights of Allah, the surrogate mother and the child, through its challenge on the principles of *Tawhid* and *Wasatiyyah*. *Tawhid* demands unwavering recognition that life, lineage, and procreation are sacred trusts governed by divine sovereignty. Additionally, *Wasatiyyah* calls Muslims to consider the lived realities of infertile couples with empathy and balance, avoiding the extremes of blind prohibition and unchecked permissiveness. Therefore, permissible alternatives such as adoption, IVF and medical treatments should be considered by married couples with challenges to conceive a child. Evidently, the challenge faced is one of the trials of the worldly abode and should be met with perseverance, patience and reliance on Allah.

In light of reproduction technologies, Islamic bioethics must evolve without eroding its metaphysical roots. As the ummah confronts more intricate medical and moral questions, *ijtihad* remains not merely a legal tool, but a spiritual imperative. It enables the community to navigate assisted reproduction—and similar issues—with both ethical clarity and theological humility. In this light, the discourse on surrogacy becomes more than a legal verdict; it becomes a mirror reflecting our commitment to uphold divine guidance while addressing human suffering with compassion, intelligence, and moral courage.

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Annexes

Annex A: Case study example on child adoption by same-sex couple

Retrieved from *Hiring a Surrogate: 6 Legal Issues for Singaporean Couples* -

SingaporeLegalAdvice.com, 2024

The image shows an Instagram post from the account 'singaporelegaladvice', which has 40.9K followers. The post features a green background with a central illustration of a man and a woman sitting on the floor with a baby. The text of the post asks, 'What do Singapore's courts consider when it comes to adopting a child?'. Below the illustration is the Singapore Legal Advice logo. The post has 78 likes and includes a caption starting with '#ICYMI' that discusses a landmark court case regarding the adoption of a biological son conceived through surrogacy in the US.

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#ICYMI 👁️ - In a recent landmark case, a gay Singaporean man was allowed to adopt his biological son who was conceived through surrogacy arrangements in the US. 🙄 Though his initial adoption application was rejected, the court ultimately granted the adoption order as doing so would be in the child's best interests.